

Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters

Deliverable D5.4

Vision of how to fund scale up solutions beyond 2025

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
ACRONYMS & ABBREVIATIONS.....	5
I. INTRODUCTION	7
II. METHODOLOGY	7
III. DEFINING FUNDING MODELS	9
IV. EUROPEAN PUBLIC FUNDING SEASCAPE.....	11
V. MAPPING OF FUNDING GAPS	20
VI. CHALLENGES WITH EXISTING FUNDING MODELS	24
VII. INNOVATIVE FUNDING MODELS.....	25
VIII. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	26
IX. BIBLIOGRAPHY	28
X. ANNEXES	30

TABLE OF FIGURES

FIGURE 1. ILLUSTRATION OF INFORMATION GATHERING AND CONSULTATIVE PREPARATION.....	8
FIGURE 2. FUNDING SPECTRUM BASED ON CHARACTER OF FINANCIAL CONTRIBUTION. THEIS & VAN LIEMPD 2024.	9
FIGURE 3. VISUAL REPRESENTATION OF THE LIFE CYCLE OF GRANTS	10
FIGURE 4. SUITABILITY OF RELEVANT FUNDING MODELS FOR KEY BUSINESS MODELS.	21
FIGURE 5. OVERVIEW OF FUNDING MODELS APPLIED BY SELECTED FUNDING INSTRUMENTS BASED ON NON-EXHAUSTIVE DESKTOP REVIEW.....	23

Executive Summary

PREP4BLUE aims to support the development of research and innovation modalities needed to achieve the objectives of the Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters. Deliverable 5.4, "Vision of how to fund scale-up solutions beyond 2025," aims to engage stakeholders in exploring and applying funding models supporting the Mission objectives.

Building on deliverable 5.2, "Business model blueprints and de-risking recommendations", relevant funding models are defined. These funding models are further explained, emphasising compact explanation and visual representation in factsheets targeted to a wider audience. A first model factsheet is annexed to this report.

Our review of the funding seascape is based on a non-exhaustive desktop review, partner input, and stakeholder consultations. It identified 19 funding instruments relevant to the Mission, excluding subordinate programmes and initiatives. To map gaps in the funding seascape, we built on the work presented in deliverable 5.2 on assessing the suitability of each funding model for specific business models and added a non-exhaustive review of the application of the defined funding models by European public funding instruments.

Deliverable 5.2 differentiates between traditional business models focused on financial and manufactured capital and sustainable business models, which preserve and create value not only for financial, manufactured, or intellectual capital but also for human, social, and natural capital (Theis & van Liempd, 2024). While Thies & van Liempd find that sustainable business models may match well with only a few funding models, we find that those funding models are clearly overrepresented in the European public funding seascape. Non-profit-oriented funding models predominate among the public funding instruments by far. Complementing those requires mobilising private funders on a large scale. Engaging private funders in support of public policy goals is essential as it has the potential to increase the pool of funding and enlarge the spectrum of funding models available for research and innovation projects. To that effect, the Mission's clear emphasis on mobilisation and engagement of societal actors and change makers is timely for mobilising private funders in support of the Mission objectives.

Our stakeholder consultation also addressed challenges experienced with existing funding models and instruments. The stakeholders consulted put less emphasis on funding gaps than on the difficulty of manoeuvring the complex funding seascape. Three concerns stood out here: the administrative burden related to application and reporting requirements, the generally long processes for obtaining funding for a relatively short period, and the difficulties with identifying and keeping track of relevant funding opportunities.

This report also lists seven examples of innovative funding models the stakeholders consulted found worth further exploring.

Finally, we present a list of recommendations for funders to consider.

Acronyms & Abbreviations

Table 1. Table of abbreviations and acronyms used in Prep4Blue and the document.

Acronym / Abbreviation	Signification
AMC	Advance Market Commitment
CEF	Connecting Europe Facility
CoE	Centres of Excellence
CFP	Common Fisheries Policy
CPMR	Conférence des régions périphériques maritimes d'Europe
EAFRD	European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development
EBRD	European Bank of Reconstruction and Development
EDF	European Defence Fund
EEA	European Economic Area
EIB	European Investment Bank
EIC	European Innovation Council
EIT	European Institute of Innovation and Technology
EMFAF	European Maritime, Fisheries, and Agriculture Fund
ERC	European Research Council
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
ESF+	European Social Fund Plus
ESIFs	European Structural and Investment Funds
EU ETS	European Union Emissions Trading System
FFF	Founder, Friends, and Family
FSTP	Financial Support to Third Parties
GNI	Gross National Income
I3	Interregional Innovation Investments
Ifremer	Institut Français de recherche pour l'exploration de la mer
JPI	Joint Programming Initiative
JPIO	Joint Programming Initiative Healthy and a Productive Seas and Oceans
JRC	Joint Research Council
KIC	Knowledge and Innovation Community
P4B	PREP4BLUE
PCP	Pre-commercial procurement
RBF	Results-based financing
RRF	Recovery and Resilience Facility
SAFE	Simple agreement for future equity
SDU	University of Southern Denmark
SMEs	Small and medium sized enterprises
S.Pro	Sustainable Projects

TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UCC	University College Cork

I. Introduction

As described in the Grant Agreement, PREP4BLUE’s overarching objective is to develop the R&I implementation modalities required to achieve the Mission objectives. The outcomes will allow the Mission Lighthouses to develop and pilot innovations of all forms.

In this context, deliverable 5.4, “Vision of how to fund scale-up solutions beyond 2025,” focuses on engaging relevant stakeholders in exchanges on how to elaborate and apply funding and business models to underpin the mission's objectives.

The deliverable contributes to PREP4BLUE’s objective 5, “*To support the creation of an enabling environment from a regulatory and economic perspective, enabling private/public investments needed in future projects*”, and specific objectives 5.1 “*Co-create Mission supportive business and governance models (for public and private actors) that will be the building blocks of pathways to a systemic change towards achieving the Mission (..)*” and 5.2 “*Develop a guide on suitable private and public funding mechanisms to be used by Mission actors, supporting coherent, integrated funding and investments for innovation and solutions for scale-up post-2025.*” The deliverable is related to *objective 3 of Work Package 5 “Create awareness of actors – that may contribute to the Mission- on different funding sources and stimulate effective exchange and coordinated uptake of these opportunities.”*

This report targets funders and decision-makers setting the policy and regulatory framework relevant for the Mission objectives. The report describes the process leading to the present deliverable, including highlighting key findings from deliverable 5.2 and the stakeholder consultations carried out. An important product accompanying this deliverable is a series of factsheets, targeting a wider audience, which presents the mapped funding models, emphasising visual representation, and a set of recommendations elaborated based on stakeholder input. The first model factsheet is annexed to this deliverable, while additional factsheets will be published in the coming months as part of a communication campaign to create awareness of funding models and related opportunities.

Partners involved:

- JPI Oceans (task lead) (JPIO)
- Conférence des régions périphériques maritimes d’Europe (CPMR)
- Institut Français de recherche pour l’exploration de la mer (Ifremer)
- Konsortium Deutsche Meeresforschung (KDM)
- Sustainable Projects (S.Pro)
- Syddansk Universitet (SDU)
- University College Cork (UCC)

II. Methodology

The information gathering and consultative part of preparing this deliverable was centred around three steps (Figure 1):

Figure 1. Illustration of the three steps used and partners involved for information gathering and consultative preparation.

Step 1: Desktop exploration of funding models, funding instruments, and funding gaps

The exploration of the funding seascape, carried out as a desktop study, defined funding models and explored European public funders' use of these models through various programmes and instruments. It was not intended to produce an exhaustive list of relevant funding instruments. In addition, an analysis of funding gaps was performed, looking at the suitability of the identified funding models for supporting projects applying the mapped business models. This work is presented in more detail in deliverable 5.2, "Business model blueprints and de-risking recommendations".

Step 2: Partner input

Funding models and funding instruments identified through the desktop study were consulted with the CSA partners, who provided additional input in writing and through a dedicated session during the project meeting in Venice in September 2023. Based on that input, the list of funding models and instruments was adapted. The inputs also formed the basis for elaborating the wider stakeholder consultation.

Step 3: Stakeholder consultation

As part of a survey prepared by CPMR for deliverable 5.1, titled "*Critical Assessment and Key Recommendations for Interregional Financing*", the partners actively contributed by proposing a question on successful funding models. This question sought input from regional authorities, specifically focusing on models relevant to the Mission's objectives. Additionally, during the Mission Arena event in Gothenburg, Sweden, held in November 2023, we organised and facilitated a stakeholder consultation workshop to seek further input. The workshop findings were further enriched by discussions with selected experts in research and innovation funding.

Following the above steps, the input collected was analysed to identify funding gaps, key obstacles experienced with existing funding models, and models suitable for achieving the Mission objectives and scale-up. These elaborations are summarised in the form of recommendations presented in this report. Additionally, the recommendations and the identified funding models will be presented through factsheets with visual representations. The factsheets will serve to create awareness among Mission-relevant actors on different funding models. A first model factsheet is attached to this report

(Annex 1). Additional ones will be released successively over the coming months as part of a communication campaign.

III. Defining funding models

Deliverable 5.2 *“Business model blueprints and de-risking recommendations”*, prepared by Jochen C. Theis and Dennis van Liempd from the University of Southern Denmark, relied on a literature review based on a non-structured snowball approach to identify funding models for mission roll-out, with a specific focus on new, innovative approaches. As shown in Figure 2, the funding models identified can be placed on an axis spanning from altruistic to profit-oriented, derived from the character of the financial contribution provided.

Figure 2. *Funding spectrum based on character of financial contribution. Theis & van Liempd 2024.*

The funding models mapped by Theis and van Liempd were analysed and discussed with relevant stakeholders, leading to a slightly amended and re-arranged list below. Notably, cascade financing and innovation vouchers were added as sub-models of donations or grants, while project financing was removed as it is not considered relevant as a funding model in this context. The funding models are listed below according to which models are typically sought at the different stages of the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) scale or maturity of a technology, service, or product. It should be noted that several of the funding models have sub-models or classes used at different maturity stages.

1. Donations or grants

Donations and grants can be made available by any type of entity and are characterised by the funder having no expectation of financial repayment or profit on the investment made. However, this does not imply a lack of expectation of non-financial deliverables or results.

Recipients of donations and grants are typically expected to report on adherence to the requirements related to the funding and on results achieved.

Figure 3. Visual representation of the life cycle of grants to be included in factsheet on Grants.

2. Concessional finance

Concessional finance refers to financial and tax instruments offering preferential terms for certain types of investments or activities. Financial guarantees are a form of concessional finance where a third party bears the risk by assuming responsibility for the creditor in case the borrower defaults on the loan.

3. Blended finance

Blended finance refers to a model in which concessional capital is provided, typically by public institutions, to reduce the risk and thereby attract commercial capital.

1.1 Cascade financing

Cascade financing is a sub-form of grants in which large funders make funding available for re-granting in the form of smaller grants by consortia that are delegated the responsibility for selecting and monitoring such smaller grants. An important advantage for the funder is to ease its part of the administration. Additionally, it enables funders to work through intermediaries with more specific thematic or geographic knowledge, and to reach target audiences which would not normally approach larger funders or are unable to absorb larger grants. Intermediaries with technical expertise may also include capacity building measures for the target group by supporting the application process or providing technical support during implementation.

1.2 Innovation vouchers

Innovation vouchers are grants provided in the form of vouchers, typically spent on access to expertise and technology needed in the innovation process. The financial support provided through these vouchers is usually limited, enabling simplified procedures for applying for and using them.

4. Equity financing

Equity financing implies that an investor receives ownership in return for an investment. There are different ways of providing equity financing, typically depending on the maturity of the company invested in. Founder, Friends and Family (FFF) funding, angel investors, venture capital, and Initial Public Offerings are examples of subcategories pertaining to a company's increasing maturity stages. Simple agreement for future equity (SAFE) is a flexible sub-form of equity that provides future equity rights without immediate valuation.

5. Debt financing

Debt financing is raising capital by borrowing funds to be repaid, typically supplemented by interest payments. Public or private financial institutions may make capital available for borrowing at preferential terms for specific purposes. There are several subcategories of debt financing, including various forms of bonds, which are debt in the form of tradable securities.

6. Pre-commercial procurement

Pre-commercial procurement (PCP) is used by public authorities to address societal challenges and meet public needs through the acquisition of innovative solutions that are not yet commercially available. PCP involves a series of competitive procurement phases from solution exploration and design to validation/testing of a limited set of first products.

7. Public procurement of innovative solutions

Public procurement of innovative solutions concerns the phase when a product, service, or process has been developed but is not yet available on a large-scale commercial basis. Thus, it is complementary as a possible next step to PCP.

8. Crowdfunding

Rather than a specific funding model, crowdfunding is an approach to other funding models where capital is raised through relatively small contributions from a relatively large number of individuals. This can be in the form of donations, loans, or equity financing.

IV. European public funding seascape

Based on a non-exhaustive desktop review and consultation with stakeholders, an exploration of the funding seascape was conducted in preparation of this deliverable. This has resulted in the following list of funding instruments of relevance to the Mission:

A. EUROPEAN STRUCTURAL AND INVESTMENT FUNDS (ESIFs)

Cohesion policy tools

1. [Cohesion Fund](#)
2. [European Regional Development Fund \(ERDF\)](#)
 - 2.1. [Interregional Innovation Investments \(I3\) Instrument](#)
 - 2.2. [Interreg Europe](#)
3. [European Social Fund Plus \(ESF+\)](#)

Agriculture and Maritime Policy Instruments

4. [European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development \(EAFRD\)](#)
5. [European Maritime, Fisheries, and Aquaculture Fund \(EMFAF\)](#)

B. EUROPEAN STRATEGIC INVESTMENTS

6. [Connecting Europe Facility \(CEF\)](#)
7. [Digital Europe Programme](#)
8. [InvestEU Programme](#)
 - 8.1. [InvestEU Blue Economy Instrument](#)

C. RESEARCH & INNOVATION

9. [EU Innovation Fund](#)
10. [Horizon Europe](#)
 - 10.1. [European Research Council \(ERC\)](#)
 - 10.2. [European Partnerships](#)
 - 10.2.1. [Biodiversa+](#)
 - 10.2.2. [Innovate SMEs / EUROSTARS](#)
 - 10.2.3. [Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership](#)
 - 10.2.4. [Zero-emission Waterborne Transport Partnership](#)
 - 10.2.5. [Water4All](#)
 - 10.3. [Pillar II Clusters and Joint Research Council \(JRC\)](#)
 - 10.4. [European Innovation Council](#)
 - 10.5. [European Institute of Innovation and Technology \(EIT\)](#)
11. [Joint Programming Initiatives](#)

D. ENVIRONMENT

12. [LIFE](#)
13. [Just Transition Fund](#)

E. OTHER INSTRUMENTS

14. [EEA and Norway Grants](#)
15. [European Bank of Reconstruction and Development \(EBRD\)](#)
16. [European Defence Fund \(EDF\)](#)
17. [European Investment Bank \(EIB\)](#)
18. [Recovery and Resilience Facility \(RRF\)](#)
19. [Single Market Programme](#)

A. EUROPEAN STRUCTURAL AND INVESTMENT FUNDS (ESIFs)

Cohesion policy tools

The Cohesion policy aims to increase the economic, social, and territorial cohesion in the European Union. To this aim, the Commission has allocated for the period 2021-27 a total of €392 billion, with €369 billion set aside for investment in jobs and growth.

1. [Cohesion Fund](#)

The Cohesion Fund supports economic and social cohesion among Member States and regions. Member States with a gross national income (GNI) below 90% of the EU average are eligible. It primarily utilises grants to support projects that contribute to the development of infrastructure, environmental protection, and sustainable growth in regions with lower income levels and facing specific challenges.

Total allocation 2021-27: €36,61 billion

2. [European Regional Development Fund \(ERDF\)](#)

The European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) enables investments in a smarter, greener, more connected, and more social Europe that is closer to its citizens. It provides grants and [equity financial instruments](#) to projects through programmes in shared responsibility between the Commission and national and regional authorities in Member States which choose which projects to finance.

Total allocation 2021-27: €313,16 billion in total for ERDF and ESF+ for the investment for jobs and growth goal.

2.1. [Interregional Innovation Investments \(I3\) Instrument](#)

Part of the ERDF, the Interregional Innovation Investments Instrument aims to support interregional innovation projects in their commercialisation and scale-up phases, giving them the tools to overcome regulatory and other barriers and arrive at the investment level.

The instrument provides support to consortia of national or regional authorities, with a particular focus on innovation authorities. It allows cascade funding through what is referred to as Financial Support to Third Parties (FSTP).

Total allocation 2021-27: €570 million

2.2. [Interreg Europe](#)

Interreg Europe is an EU co-funded programme promoting regional development through interregional cooperation to reduce development, growth, and quality of life disparities. The programme covers 36 countries and provides support for public authorities, business organisations, environmental organisations, and education and research institutions.

Total allocation 2021-2027: €394 million

3. [European Social Fund Plus \(ESF+\)](#)

The European Social Fund Plus (ESF+) supports the EU's employment, social, education and skills policies, including structural reforms in these areas. ESF+ is mainly managed under shared management, with the Member States implementing approximately €98,5 billion. ESF+ provides support through grants and financial instruments such as equity investments, loans, guarantees or other risk-sharing financial packages. The use of financial instruments is strengthened for the 2021-27 period, with the potential for funds to be reused for further investment.

Total allocation 2021-27: €99,3 billion

Agriculture and Maritime Policy Instruments

4. [European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development \(EAFRD\)](#)

The European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) is a funding arm of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and was established to support rural development. It finances the EU's contribution to national or regional rural development programmes with three main objectives:

- improving the competitiveness of agriculture;
- encouraging sustainable management of natural resources and climate action;
- achieving a balanced territorial development of rural economies and communities.

Grants and subsidies are the primary types of financing provided by the EAFRD through the Rural Development Programmes. They are allocated to support rural development initiatives and improve agriculture, environmental sustainability, and rural areas. The EAFRD can also provide investment support for rural enterprises and projects through [financial instruments](#), such as loans, microcredits, guarantees, or equity.

While primarily focused on agriculture, the EAFRD can support areas of relevance for the Mission. These include water management, ecosystem preservation, generation of employment opportunities, food and health, digitisation, sustainable coastal farming, and the development of rural coastal communities.

Total allocation 2021-27: €95.5 billion.

5. [European Maritime, Fisheries, and Aquaculture Fund \(EMFAF\)](#)

The European Maritime, Fisheries, and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF) supports the EU common fisheries policy (CFP), the EU maritime policy and the EU agenda for international ocean governance. EMFAF supports projects that contribute to the sustainable exploitation and management of aquatic and maritime resources.

EMFAF utilises grants and [financial instruments](#) such as loans, guarantees, equity or a combination of measures to support projects to ensure fisheries' long-term viability, promote sustainable aquaculture practices, protect marine ecosystems, and foster economic growth in coastal areas.

The EMFAF is specifically designed to support sustainable fisheries, aquaculture, and the development of coastal communities engaged in the blue economy. It provides financial assistance for projects that promote sustainable practices, protect marine ecosystems, and enhance economic growth in coastal areas.

Total allocation 2021-27: €6,1 billion

B. EUROPEAN STRATEGIC INVESTMENTS

6. [Connecting Europe Facility \(CEF\)](#)

The Connecting Europe Facility (CEF) aims to improve Europe's infrastructure networks in the fields of transport, energy, and digital connectivity. CEF supports projects that enhance the interoperability and integration of these networks, promoting a more connected and integrated European Union.

In addition to grants, the CEF offers financial support to projects through innovative financial instruments such as guarantees and project bonds. The CEF can provide financial support for improving maritime transport infrastructure, enhancing port facilities, and optimising the efficiency of maritime logistics systems, thereby boosting the connectivity and competitiveness of the blue economy.

Total allocation 2021-27: €33,71 billion (transport €25,81 billion, energy €5,84 billion, digital €2,07 billion)

7. SFS Digital Europe Programme

The Digital Europe Programme aims to strengthen Europe's digital capabilities and competitiveness. It provides grants to projects in five areas: supercomputing, artificial intelligence, cybersecurity, advanced digital skills, and ensuring the wide use of digital technologies across the economy and society. The latter area indicates a relevance for the Mission, e.g. in relation to the Digital Twin of the Ocean.

Total allocation 2021-27: €7,6 billion

8. InvestEU Programme

The InvestEU Programme supports sustainable investment, innovation, and job creation in Europe. Through the InvestEU Fund, it aims to mobilise more than €372 billion of public and private investment. This will be achieved by making available an EU budget guarantee of €26.2 billion to de-risk investments of 11 implementing partners such as the European Investment Bank (EIB) and other financial institutions. The programme supports four main policy areas including blue economy aspects.

Total allocation 2021-27: Aims to mobilise more than €372 billion of public and private investment through an EU budget guarantee of €26.2 billion.

8.1. InvestEU Blue Economy Instrument

The InvestEU Blue Economy Instrument is building on the BlueInvest Fund pilot. It combines the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund, the EIB Group and InvestEU finance. The aim of this equity initiative is to mobilise an additional €500 million of EU funds for financial intermediaries investing in the Blue Economy sector. This is expected to result in €1.5 billion of risk financing available to Blue Economy SMEs and startups via financial intermediaries. The initiative supports research, development, demonstration, upscaling, commercialisation and scaling of clean technologies or environmental sustainability solutions that contribute to EU Green Deal objectives.

C. RESEARCH & INNOVATION

9. EU Innovation Fund

The EU Innovation Fund supports the development and deployment of innovative low-carbon technologies in Europe. It focuses on projects related to renewable energy, energy-intensive industries, and energy storage, with the goal of helping the EU transition to a more sustainable and climate-neutral economy. The EU Innovation Fund utilises grants, competitive bidding, and blended finance, combining grants and concessional financing.

The EU Innovation Fund can support innovative projects in the blue economy sector, such as developing and deploying sustainable technologies for ocean energy, aquaculture, and marine environmental protection.

Total allocation: The EU Emissions Trading System (EU ETS) funds the Innovation Fund through the sale of carbon allowances, with funding depending on the carbon price. From 2020 to 2030, it may amount to €40 billion, calculated using a carbon price of €75/tCO₂.

10. [Horizon Europe](#)

Horizon Europe is the EU's key programme for funding research and innovation. Horizon Europe primarily provides grants for research and innovation projects, ranging from fundamental research to technological development and market deployment.

While Mission Ocean and Waters spans across programmes, policies, and governance levels, it is rooted in Horizon Europe.

Specific Mission calls under the HE Work Programmes 2021-23 had a budget of €114,3 million in 2021, €117,9 million in 2022, and €111,9 million in 2023.

Total allocation 2021-27: €95,5 billion

10.1. [European Research Council \(ERC\)](#)

The European Research Council (ERC) funds excellent frontier research through four core grant schemes: [Starting Grants](#), [Consolidator Grants](#), [Advanced Grants](#) and [Synergy Grants](#). In addition, the ERC offers [Proof of Concept Grants](#) for exploring the commercial or societal potential of results from a researcher's previous ERC project.

Total allocation 2021-27: More than €16 billion

10.2. [European Partnerships](#)

European Partnerships allow the European Commission and private and/or public partners to pool their resources and work together to address some of Europe's most pressing challenges. The first Strategic Plan of Horizon Europe included 49 European Partnerships. In 2023, the Commission presented proposals for ten new candidate Partnerships. There are three types of partnerships: co-programmed, co-funded, and institutionalised. Partnerships relevant to the Mission include:

10.2.1. [Biodiversa+](#)

Biodiversa+ is a co-funded European partnership dedicated to impactful biodiversity research. Aligned with the European Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, its objective is to facilitate transformative change by linking science, policy, and practical applications.

Total allocation: €800 million

10.2.2. Innovate SMEs / EUROSTARS

Innovative SMEs /EUROSTARS is a co-funded European partnership implemented by EUREKA. EUROSTARS provides grants to research and development projects carried out by small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in collaboration with research institutions. It aims to foster innovation and enhance the competitiveness of European SMEs by providing financial support for the development of new products, processes, and services.

Total allocation: €250 million expected public-private investment each year

10.2.3. Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership

The Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership (SBEP) is a Horizon Europe co-funded partnership through which more than 60 partner institutions from 26 countries and the European Commission pool research and innovation investments and align national programmes at a pan-European scale. The Partnership aims to boost the transformation towards a climate-neutral, sustainable, productive, and competitive blue economy and restore the ocean's health, resilience, and services to people by enabling climate-neutral, sustainable, and productive economic activity. The Partnership will provide grants to consortia through 6 calls for proposals.

Total allocation 2022-2029: €450 million

10.2.4. Zero-emission Waterborne Transport Partnership

Waterborne is a co-programmed European Partnership that will demonstrate zero-emission solutions for all main ship types and services before 2030 to enable zero-emission waterborne transport before 2050. Funding is provided through annual calls for proposals.

Total estimated allocation 2021-30: Up to € 1.23 billion

10.2.5. Water4All

Water4All - Water Security for the Planet- is a co-funded European Partnership for freshwater research, bringing together 90 partners from 33 countries. The partnership aims to tackle water challenges to face climate change, help achieve the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals, and boost the EU's competitiveness and growth. The partnership publishes calls for proposals annually.

Total estimated allocation: €112 million

10.3. Pillar II Clusters and Joint Research Council (JRC)

Pillar II of Horizon Europe, "Global Challenges and European Industrial Competitiveness," comprises the JRC and six clusters: Health; Culture, Creativity and Inclusive Society; Civil Security for Society; Digital, Industry and Space; Climate, Energy and Mobility; Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment.

Total allocation 2021-27: € 53.5 billion

10.4. European Innovation Council

The European Innovation Council (EIC), established under Horizon Europe, is an innovation programme to identify, develop and scale up breakthrough technologies and innovations, including in [areas of relevance for the Mission](#) such as renewable energy and biotechnology. It provides funding for individual companies (mainly startups and SMEs) through grants and investments. The investments take the form of direct equity or quasi-equity investments and are managed by the [EIC Fund](#).

Allocation 2023: €1,6 billion

10.5. European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT)

EIT is part of Horizon Europe's pillar III. EIT offers grants, courses, workshops, and services to support entrepreneurship, business creation, scale-up and acceleration. The brunt of EITs budget funds the Knowledge and Innovation Communities (KICs).

Total allocation 2021-27: € 2,96 billion

11. Joint Programming Initiatives

Joint Programming Initiatives (JPIs) aim to better align national strategies, policies, and programmes, including the approximately 85 percent of research and innovation investments spent at the national level¹. Member countries agree on joint research programming activities on a voluntary basis. The 10 JPIs cover major research fields that tackle the Grand Societal Challenges, including oceans, climate, and water.

Providing grants through Joint Calls is one of the JPIs' implementation tools. The most relevant JPIs for the Mission are JPI Oceans and Water JPI.

The total allocation of each JPI varies considerably. More information on the individual allocation of each JPI can be found on the respective websites.

D. ENVIRONMENT

12. LIFE

LIFE is the EU's programme for environmental and climate action. It supports initiatives that contribute to the protection of nature, the transition to a circular economy, the fight against climate change, and the promotion of environmental awareness and governance. LIFE provides [six different types of grants](#), including operating grants for those involved in the development, implementation and enforcement of Union legislation and policy; technical assistance for capacity building; strategic integrated project grants to implement strategies or action plans and other types of projects supporting the objectives of the LIFE programme.

¹ [Joint-Programming-Initiatives_joint-brochure.pdf \(jpi-urbaneurope.eu\)](#)

Many of the environmental and climate action projects funded by LIFE are relevant to the Mission. This includes initiatives focused on marine conservation, coastal zone management, marine pollution prevention, and the promotion of sustainable coastal tourism.

Total allocation 2021-27: €5,45 billion

13. Just Transition Fund

The Just Transition Fund supports regions and communities that are heavily dependent on fossil fuel industries and are undergoing a transition towards a more sustainable and climate-friendly economy. The Fund supports investments in areas such as digital connectivity, clean energy technologies, emissions reduction, industrial site regeneration, worker reskilling, and technical assistance. It primarily uses grants to create new job opportunities and foster sustainable economic activities.

Total allocation 2021-27: €19,24 billion

OTHER INSTRUMENTS

14. EEA and Norway Grants

The EEA and Norway Grants are funding mechanisms established by Iceland, Liechtenstein, and Norway in cooperation with the EU. They aim to reduce social and economic disparities within the European Economic Area (EEA). The EEA and Norway Grants provide project grants for e.g. innovation, research, education, and competitiveness; social inclusion and youth employment; environment, energy, climate change; and civil society. The primary focus is on the 15 countries eligible for the EU Cohesion Fund.

Total allocation 2014-21: €2,8 billion (negotiations for 2021+ are ongoing)

15. European Bank of Reconstruction and Development (EBRD)

The European Bank of Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) supports projects that contribute to the development of the private sector and promote economic growth and stability. It covers a range of sectors, including energy, natural resources, infrastructure, transport, and tourism. It offers several financial instruments, with the principal forms of direct financing being loans, equity and guarantees. EBRD also opens for cascade funding or assistance through financial intermediaries. Intermediaries include banks in which the EBRD has an equity stake or with which it has signed a loan and investment or venture capital funds in which the EBRD has made an investment.

The EBRD works in 39 countries, including 13 EU Member States.

Total allocation 2023: projected investment in the range of €10,5 to €11,5 billion

16. European Defence Fund (EDF)

The European Defence Fund (EDF) is an EU funding mechanism to enhance defence cooperation, capability development, and research and innovation in the defence sector. It aims to strengthen the EU's strategic autonomy. EDF support is provided mainly through grants.

Total allocation 2014-21: Close to €8 billion

17. European Investment Bank (EIB)

As the lending arm of the EU, the European Investment Bank (EIB) is the largest multilateral financial institution in the world. The EIB raises long-term funds by issuing bonds in international capital markets. Ninety percent of its funding is directed towards promoting sustainable growth and job creation in the EU Member States.

The EIB provides loans, guarantees and equity.

Total allocation 2023: Global borrowing authorisation for 2023 is up to €50 billion

18. Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF)

The Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) is a temporary instrument of the EU to facilitate recovery from the COVID-19 pandemic. Through the RRF, the Commission issues bonds to borrow funds from the capital markets to support European economic recovery and the green and digital transitions. Through the RRF, Member States get access to up to €227 billion for grants and up to €385 billion for loans.

Maximum programme envelope: €806.9 billion

19. Single Market Programme

The Single Market Programme focuses on strengthening the governance of the internal market, supporting the competitiveness of industry and in particular of micro, small and medium-sized enterprises, promoting human, animal and plant health and animal welfare.

Support is provided through grants, guarantees, loans and equity financing.

Total allocation 2021-27: €4,2 billion

V. Mapping of funding gaps

The literature review carried out by Jochen C. Theis and Dennis van Liempd (University of Southern Denmark) as part of *deliverable 5.2 “Business model blueprints and de-risking recommendations”* resulted in the list of funding models included in Figure 4 below. Funding models relevant for sustainability projects in general and for Mission roll-out specifically were analysed, notably in terms of their suitability for key business models.

To identify funding gaps, Theis and van Liempd rated the suitability of each funding model for each of the business models on a scale from 0-4, resulting in the heat map in Figure 4. The authors set the rating by expert judgement, building on insights from literature, stakeholder dialogue, expert interviews, and their own professional judgment. Based on this, they found that for each business model there exists at least one funding model that seems very suitable and further funding models that are suitable to varying degrees.

Business model	Donation	Public Funding	Public-private partnership	Product	Service	Subscription	Remanufacturing	Repair	Upgrading	Functional economy
Funding model										
Donations	Green	Yellow	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Yellow
Grants	Yellow	Green	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Green	Green	Green	Green
FFF-finance	Yellow	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
Angel investors	Red	Red	Yellow	Green	Green	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
Venture capital	Red	Red	Yellow	Green	Green	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
IPO	Red	Red	Yellow	Green	Green	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
Senior/junior debt	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
GSSS bonds	Red	Red	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Green	Green	Green	Green
Crowdfunding	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
Cascade finance	Yellow	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
Concessional finance	Red	Red	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
Blended finance	Yellow	Yellow	Green	Green	Green	Yellow	Green	Green	Green	Green
Project finance	Red	Yellow	Green	Green	Green	Yellow	Green	Green	Green	Green
Pre-commercial procurement	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Yellow
Public procurement	Red	Green	Yellow	Green	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow

Figure 4. Suitability of relevant funding models for key business models. Heat map that graphically expresses the suitability of relevant funding models for key business models. Colour-coded ratings of 0 and 1 in red, of 2 and 3 yellow, and of 4 green. The greener the column, the more funding opportunities are suitable for a business model. The red areas in a column indicate the risk of a funding gap for a specific business model. (Theis & van Liempd, 2024.).

In detail, however, the analysis also reveals systematic differences between business model categories. Notably, relatively few funding models match well with the not-for-profit business model category, i.e., donation and public funding. Not-for-profit projects based on these business models are less able to deliver the return on investment expected by profit-oriented donors and, therefore, fit best with funding models at the altruistic end of the scale.

A larger number of funding models seem to be fit for business models within the public-private partnership category. In contrast, the for-profit business models generally match well with the highest number of funding models.

In general, funding models and projects that can be placed at the same end of the altruistic – profit-oriented scale match well. Funding models on the altruistic end of the scale may include restrictions on generating profit within supported projects, underscoring the mismatch with for-profit projects. By contrast, funding models on the altruistic end of the scale match well with projects applying a not-for-profit business model. Likewise, the expectation of return on investments characterising funders

applying profit-oriented funding models is a natural match for projects based on a profit-making business model, whereas not-for-profit projects will struggle to deliver such a return.

Theis and van Liempd conclude that the suitability of a funding model depends on the specific characteristics of a project and that projects of a profit-making nature have a wider choice of matching funding models. Notably, they found that traditional business models (e.g., product or service) matched well with the most funding models and achieved the highest score sums. Sustainable business models, less profit-oriented by being willing to sacrifice profit in favour of an ecological or social outcome, may not be able to attract funders focused on returns and, therefore, applying profit-oriented funding models.

However, an exploration of the funding seascape, performed by JPI Oceans and based on stakeholder consultations and a non-exhaustive desktop review (Figure 5), found that funding models on the altruistic end of the scale are predominant among European public funding instruments, thereby ensuring available funding for implementing and upscaling solutions within a not-for-profit business model.

Several considerations can plausibly explain the overrepresentation of more altruistic funding models in the European public funding seascape.

Financing public goods and needs, including ecological and social progress, is a natural part of public funders' mission and mandate. This can be done without any expectation of financial return on investment. In contrast, private investors generally have a profit-oriented nature, which limits their ability to make a one-way transfer of funds. Private funders and foundations also engage in non-profit and philanthropic activities but typically have a narrower mandate and more limited budget than public funders as they cannot raise funds from taxes but rely on owners or benefactors for financing.

While some of the stakeholders we consulted pointed out mismatches between policy objectives, regulatory framework, and available public funding, policy goals and public funding are nevertheless directly linked. Private funders, on the other hand, can set their funding objectives at their own discretion, independent of public policy objectives. Engaging private funders in support of public policy goals consequently not only has the potential to increase the pool of funding but also to enlarge the spectrum of funding models available for research and innovation projects. Initiatives with a strong emphasis on mobilisation and engagement of wider groups of stakeholders as enablers, as pursued in the Mission, could be successful in capitalising on the untapped potential of mobilising private funders to support public policy objectives.

Funding instruments			Type of funding model										
			Grants	Cascade	Concessional finance	Blended finance	Equity financing	Debt financing	Pre-commercial procurement	Public procurement of innovative solutions	Crowd-funding		
European Structural and Investment Funds	Cohesion Policy Tools	Cohesion Fund	█										
		European Regional Development Fund	█				█						
		Interregional Innovation Investment (IS) Instrument		█									
		European Social Fund Plus	█		█		█	█					
	Agriculture and Maritime Policy Instruments	European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD)	█		█		█	█					
		European Maritime, Fisheries, and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF)	█				█	█					
European Strategic Investments	Connecting Europe Facility (CEF)		█		█			█					
	Digital Europe Programme		█										
	InvestEU	InvestEU Blue Economy Instrument	█		█	█	█	█					
Research & Innovation	EU Innovation Fund		█		█	█							
	Horizon Europe	European Research Council		█									
		European Partnerships	Blodiversa+		█								
			Innovate SMEs / EUROSARS		█								
			Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership		█								
			Zero-emission Waterborne Transport Partnership		█								
			Water4All		█								
	Pillar II Clusters and Joint Research Council (JRC)		█										
	European Innovation Council		█										
	European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT)		█				█						
Joint Programming Initiatives		█											
Environment	LIFE		█										
	Just Transition Fund		█										
Other	EEA and Norway Grants		█	█									
	European Bank of Reconstruction and Development (EBRD)			█	█		█	█					
	European Defence Fund		█										
	European Investment Bank				█		█	█					
	Recovery and Resilience Fund				█		█	█					
	Single Market Programme		█				█	█					

Figure 5. Overview of funding models applied by selected funding instruments based on non-exhaustive desktop review.

Inputs from the survey performed by CPMR among regional authorities as part of PREP4BLUE’s deliverable 5.1, “Critical assessment and key recommendations for Interregional financing”, emphasise funding opportunities targeted at the regional level or decentralised to be managed at the regional level. Although the sampling was limited, project examples provided indicated that regional authorities are key actors in financing impactful projects in the field of research and innovation that

contribute to the achievement of the Mission Ocean objectives. In particular, regions that target R&I investments in the blue economy sector in their Smart Specialisation Strategies maximise funding opportunities in innovation for a sustainable blue economy.

VI. Challenges with existing funding models

The stakeholder consultation carried out as part of this task included questions on challenges or obstacles experienced with existing funding models. The stakeholder input received largely relates to grants, which likely reflects the predominant grants-based experience of the stakeholders consulted. While stakeholders identify numerous challenges with funding models applied by European public funders, there is a clear wish for a continued strong presence of public funding, often coming in the form of grants. Notably, in the first phases of research and innovation, where it is difficult to attract private investments, the role of public funding is crucial to fill the gap, as well as to reduce risk and thereby attract private capital. Public investments can also play a role in mobilising private capital through other means than direct investments in projects, such as the creation of networking spaces or organising awareness or communication campaigns highlighting private investment opportunities in specific sectors or regions.

The main obstacles reported, notably with grants, concern the administrative burden related to application and reporting procedures. As most researchers must work on multiple projects simultaneously, often financed by different funding instruments and spanning across several funding models, they must invest extensive time in exploring funding opportunities, learning the requirements, preparing applications, and ensuring reporting during and after implementation. Administrative work affects the time available to work on research and project content. The time aspect is emphasised, not only in terms of the time investment into project preparation and reporting but also the generally long time span from the start of proposal preparation to grant decision and payment. There is a demand for fast-track solutions for smaller grants and pressing topics. Funding gaps between projects and cash-flow issues related to the payment schedules were raised as problems for both private innovators and civil society organisations. The relatively short-term perspective of most funding schemes is particularly challenging for some sectors, such as primary production (aquaculture) that require long-term financing and concessions for space. Civil society representatives also underlined NGOs' need for predictable operational financing and their challenges in meeting co-financing requirements.

Concerning the scope of existing funding opportunities, stakeholders pointed to the difficulty in finding financing for existing businesses, as funding mainly targets start-ups and innovation. There is also a potential mismatch between funders focusing on upscaling and businesses wishing to diversify to reduce risk. Private sector stakeholders claimed that funding opportunities are characterised by a lack of business involvement in setting the research funding agenda.

Stakeholders report that funding opportunities need to be complemented by incubators or other mechanisms providing mentorship and guidance, including manoeuvring the funding seascape, business support services, and networking opportunities. This could also be combined with access to finance, as in Ifremer's annual [Octo'pousse](#) competition. Stakeholders also call for better coordination and exchanges between different funders, including between European, national and regional level funders.

It is noteworthy that stakeholders in our consultations have put less emphasis on funding gaps than on the difficulty of manoeuvring the complexities of the existing funding seascape. It may, therefore, be worth exploring additional support measures to help stakeholders find which funding models suit their needs and subsequently identify available funding instruments. Additionally, modalities in support of exploiting the potential of unsuccessful proposals, such as seals of excellence for high-quality non-funded proposals, can reduce the administrative burden of applicants by clearly building on existing proposals when seeking out new funding opportunities.

VII. Innovative funding models

Stakeholders have suggested a range of new or innovative funding models that could be worth further exploring for funders looking to contribute to the Mission objectives and scale up. The suggestions included:

1. Results-based financing

Results-based funding (RBF) implies that funding is provided contingent upon achieving specific, predefined results or outcomes defined by the funder and the grantee together. The approach may foster innovation, efficiency, and flexibility as the grantee has more freedom in finding how to achieve the results. RBF also requires less emphasis on monitoring by the funder during implementation as the focus is on accountability for results, not process. The new lump-sum model in Horizon Europe is moving funding schemes in this direction.

2. Prizes or awards

Prizes or awards are well-known as a model for funding specific goals or rewarding excellence. This funding model, often referred to as "prize-based funding", can effectively stimulate innovation by encouraging competition and generating visibility. By defining precise goals, funders can ensure that contributors focus their efforts on solving particular challenges motivated by a monetary award, publicity, and recognition.

Similar to results-based funding, prize-based funding rewards actual achievements rather than activities or work performed. Funds are consequently spent on solutions that have been proven successful.

A notable example is the [Ansari XPRIZE](#), which helped kickstart a new private space industry by awarding USD 10 million for the creation of a reliable, reusable, privately financed, crewed spaceship. A more recent example is the [Vesuvius Challenge](#), offering various rewards for those contributing to virtually unwrapping the carbonized papyrus scrolls of Herculaneum.

3. Residency grants

Residency grants are a form of award provided to *e.g.* researchers to allow them to focus on their project within a specific environment. They typically include accommodation, financial support, and access to infrastructure and professional networks or guidance. This gives recipients the time, space, and resources needed to focus on creativity, innovation, and professional development.

4. Advance market commitments

Advance Market Commitments (AMCs) are intended to stimulate the development and delivery of products that are important for society but have too uncertain demand or profitability to be otherwise realised by commercial market mechanisms, such as certain types

of vaccines or medicines. By committing to purchasing a certain amount of such a product for a fixed price, AMCs incentivise private investment in their research and development.

5. Lotteries

A lottery system implies that grant recipients are randomly selected from a pool of proposals which meet a given level of quality. This funding model introduces an element of chance into the funding decision, traditionally solely relying on peer-review processes. This could reduce bias and facilitate equal opportunities. Knowing that there is an element of chance in funding decisions may also encourage more innovative, high-risk projects that researchers otherwise would deem too unconventional to propose for traditional funding.

6. Centres of Excellence schemes

Research Centres of Excellence (CoE) are designated centres organised for a specific purpose or part of an existing institution dedicated to achieving scientific excellence in a specific field. CoEs bring together leading experts and researchers to play a central role in advancing knowledge and fostering innovation in their fields. Such centres can also take on roles in policy advice, education, and training. CoEs are typically selected through a competitive call, securing their funding for a longer term than most funding schemes would.

7. Closed call for proposals

Funders may organise calls for proposals that are only open for projects that have already been granted support. Granting additional funds for projects to scale up or continue their activities beyond what was initially foreseen can be an effective means for funders to reduce administration costs and enhance the impact of their funding. The ERC Proof of Concept grants apply this model.

VIII. Conclusions and recommendations

Based on our findings from the review of the European funding seascape and the input from the stakeholder consultations, we invite funders to consider the following recommendations:

- **Ensure coordination and alignment of funding models and business models**
 - Improve coordination between regional, national, and European funders to reduce overlaps and gaps and exchange best practices.
 - Sustainable business models are well-supported by European public funding instruments. However, private funders need to be engaged in support of the Mission objectives to increase the pool of funding and enlarge the spectrum of funding models available for research and innovation projects.
 - Ensure real involvement of business and industry in setting the research agenda as a starting point for increasing private funding.
- **Ramp-up support services for navigating a complex funding seascape**
 - Enhance support systems for researchers and innovators navigating the complex funding seascape.
 - Upscale initiatives providing fundraising assistance, coaching, matchmaking, market uptake facilitation, and other services for start-ups and innovators, such as BlueInvest.

- Put particular emphasis on supporting researchers in manoeuvring the path from research funding to innovation funding and commercialisation.
- Strengthen innovative mechanisms to ease fundraising efforts, such as seals of excellence for non-funded project proposals evaluated to be of good quality.

- **Establish faster and leaner opportunities**
 - Simplify administrative requirements in general.
 - Make available fast-track support schemes with reduced administrative requirements for smaller grants.

- **Innovate**
 - Public funders should explore the underused potential of applying profit-oriented funding models while retaining the funding models on the altruistic side of the spectrum.
 - Explore innovative funding models, such as results-based funding, with the potential of reducing the administrative burden of applicants, while keeping due care to avoid further complicating an already complex funding seascape.

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X. ANNEXES

Annex 1: first model factsheet on Cascade funding

EU MISSIONS

RESTORE OUR OCEAN AND WATERS

CASCADE FINANCING

Cascade financing is a form of grants in which large funders allow grantees to pass parts or all of it on in smaller portions. The intermediary takes the responsibility for the selection and monitoring of such smaller grants.

This eases the funder's part of the administration and enables working through intermediaries with more specific thematic or geographic knowledge. This way, funders can reach target groups which would not normally approach larger funders or are unable to absorb larger grants.

Intermediaries with technical expertise may also include capacity building measures for the target group by supporting the application process or providing technical support during implementation.

To restore our ocean and waters, civil society is crucial both in finding the solutions needed and ensuring the legitimacy of the green transition. By allocating our funds for civil society through national Fund Operators, independent of government, we can rely on strong sectorial and national expertise while local NGOs seeking funds get guidance in their own language.

Ragna, EEA and Norway Grants

